

A Review Of Instrumental Analytical Methods To Assay Active Ingredients In Multicomponent Pharmaceutical Formulation & Agricultural Matrices

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ABSTRACT

The development and formulation of the pharmaceuticals brought a revolution in human health. These pharmaceuticals would help their intent only if they are free from impurities and are administered in an appropriate quantity. Hence, there are having many challenges and it can be reduced by effective use of excipients, which permits formulators to overcome these challenges. So, various chemical and instrumental methods were developed to make drugs serve their purpose at regular intervals which are involved in the estimation of drugs. These pharmaceuticals may develop impurities at various steps of their development, transportation and storage, which makes the pharmaceutical risky to be administered thus they must be identified and quantitated. For this analytical instrumentation and methods play an important role. This review highlights the role of the analytical instrumentation and analytical techniques, such as titrimetric, chromatographic, spectroscopic, electrophoretic, and electrochemical and their corresponding methods that have been applied in the analysis of pharmaceuticals for assessing the quality of the drugs.

Keywords: Instrumental analysis, Environmental protection, chemical pollutants, Air monitoring, Water quality, Soil analysis, Favipiravir, Ritonavir, Corona virus.

1.INTRODUCTION

Microplastics (MPs), which are tiny plastic particles smaller than 5 mm, are becoming a major environmental concern due to their widespread occurrence in the environment. These polymers have been identified in both terrestrial and marine environments. MPs can negatively impact ecosystems and human health because they are a vector for dangerous substances. Additionally, they are commonly eaten by wildlife and remain in the environment for decades. One of the primary causes of the underreporting of microplastic (MP) pollution in the agricultural environment is the absence of appropriate and reliable analytical techniques.

Understanding the quantity and effects of microplastic pollution requires accurate quantification and identification of MPs in diverse environmental matrices because plastics vary in composition and properties based on the type of polymer. These days, methods other than physical analysis, such as hand picking and flotation, can be used to identify and quantify MPs in environmental samples. Because of their small size and low concentration, MPs require the use of advanced analytical techniques. Wet analysis techniques (destructive analysis) gave way to the use of modern analytical tools (non-destructive analysis) as chemical analysis evolved over time.

Due to their high cost and requirement for highly qualified analysts to conduct the analysis and interpret the data, Raman spectroscopy and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy are effective non-destructive techniques for identifying MPs based on their chemical composition and structure in a variety of environments.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy is a widely used technique for MP analysis due to its high sensitivity and specificity. This technique measures a sample's absorbance or transmission of infrared radiation. For instance, the signal at 1700 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of a carbonyl group in the microplastic structure. The Raman spectroscopy technique is used to measure the scattered light that results from exposing a sample to a laser beam. Raman spectroscopy can provide information about the chemical composition and structure of MPs based on their unique Raman spectra. This approach has been used to analyze MPs in samples of biota, sediment, and seawater.

Pyrolysis–Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectroscopy (Pyr/GC/MS) is an analytical technique that involves a sample's controlled thermal breakdown, followed by the separation and identification of the pyrolysis products using mass spectrometry and gas chromatography. The sample is destroyed during the pyrolysis process, despite the fact that chromatography techniques are very sensitive and can yield quantitative information on the chemical composition of MPs. Using flow cytometry (FC), one can ascertain the MPs' size distribution and concentration in a sample. FC has obviously been used for MP analysis in watery environments, but not in matrices of soil and compost. Numerous microscopy methods have been used to identify and describe MPs.

Based on their visual characteristics, optical microscopy techniques such as stereomicroscopy and polarized light microscopy (PLM) are commonly used to identify and count particles. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) provide higher-resolution images for analyzing the surface appearance and structure of MPs. In experimental settings, previous research has shown the advantages and disadvantages of different approaches in terms of accuracy/recovery rate, turnaround time, project goal, cost-benefit effectiveness, and anticipated results. This review study's objective is to provide a comparative analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of various instrumental analytical techniques for MPs in three environmental matrices: compost, soil, and aquatic.

2. ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES

2.1 TITRIMETRIC TECHNIQUES

Titrimetric method of analysis was invented in the year 1835 by Gay–Lussac, the volumetric method which consequently leads to the origin of term titration. Now, there some innovation methods were being used, i.e.,

spreading of non-aqueous titration method, expanding the field of application of titrimetric methods to weak acids, bases and potentiometric end point detection enhancing the precision of the methods. Through the development of functional group analysis procedures titrimetric methods have been shown to be beneficial in kinetic measurements which are in turn applied to establish reaction rates. It has some advantages which include saving time and labour, also more precise method, the reason that is no need of using reference standards. For instances, in the past captopril, albendazole and gabapentin in commercial dosage forms was determined by titrimetric methods. The non-aqueous titration method has been used for determination of Pefloxacin. Besides its application in drug estimation titrimetric was used in the past for the estimation of degradation products of the pharmaceuticals.

2.2 CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUES

Chromatography was invented by Russian botanist Tswett in 1903. During 1970's, most chemical separations were carried out using a variety of techniques including open-column chromatography, paper chromatography, and thin-layer chromatography.

Mainly, chromatography is a separation technique that separates mixtures into individual components by using mobile phase and stationary phase. The various constituents of the mixture travel at different speeds for causing them to separate. The separation is based on differential partitioning between the mobile and stationary phases. When the stationary phase is a solid support of adsorptive nature and mobile phase is liquid or gaseous phase it is called adsorption Chromatography. Analytical chromatography is done normally with smaller amounts of material and is for measuring the relative proportions of analytes in a mixture. According to USP chromatography can be defined as a procedure by which solute is separated by a differential migration process in a system consisting of two or more phases, one of which move continuously in a given direction.

Fig.2.2.1: Chromotography

2.2.1. THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) is an old technique, In TLC, a solid phase, the adsorbent, is coated onto a solid support as a thin layer usually on a glass, plastic, or aluminium support. TLC is based on a multistage distribution process, which involves a suitable “adsorbent” (the stationary phase), solvents or solvent mixtures (the mobile phase or eluent), and the sample molecules. Here, various factors determined the efficiency of this type of chromatographic separation. First the adsorbent should show extreme selectivity toward the substances being separated so as to the dissimilarities in the rate of elution be large. For the separation of any given mixture, some adsorbents may be too strongly adsorbing or too weakly adsorbing

TLC is a powerful tool for simultaneous estimation of multicomponent formulation and for selection of unknown materials in bulk drugs. The high specificity of TLC has been exploited to quantitative analytical purpose using spot elution followed by spectrophotometric measurement. TLC has distinctive advantages such as low-cost, small sample clean-up, wide range of mobile phases, flexibility in sample separation and high sample loading capacity etc. TLC can be used for the determination of some steroid's pioglitazone, celecoxib, noscapine and impurities of pharmaceuticals can be identified and determined.

2.2.2. HIGH-PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY (HPLC)

HPLC is an advanced technique of liquid chromatography, determine first time in the year 1980, for the assay of bulk drug materials. Here, HPLC methods used for separating the complex mixture of molecules encountered in chemical and biological systems, in order to recognize better the role of individual molecules.

The specificity of the HPLC method is excellent and simultaneously sufficient precision and accuracy are also achievable. During the literature survey, it was observed that HPLC has been the most widely used system among the chromatographic techniques. the estimation of high-performance liquid chromatography of different dosage forms with mobile phase, which are taken by some of the reviewed publications. Mainly, UV detector is widely used in HPLC, which has ability to monitor several wavelengths simultaneously; it is possible only via allowing a multiple wavelength scanning program. If available in sufficient quantity, UV detector assures all the UV-absorbing components are detected. Second is photodiode array (PDA) detector which is set at the image plane of a spectrometer to apply a range of wavelengths to be detected concurrently. Sample must be injected numerous times with changing wavelength, while a variable Wavelength detector (VWD) is used and all the peaks are to be detected. When PDA detector is used a wavelength range can be programmed and all the compounds that absorb within this range can be identified in a single analysis. PDA detector can also be used to analyse peak purity by matching spectra within a peak. PDA detector used for determination of Iloperidone in pharmaceuticals.

The refractive index detector is the detector of choice when one needs to detect analytes with restricted or no UV absorption such as alcohols, sugars, carbohydrates, fatty acids, and polymers. Thus, refractive detector utilized to analyse the content of volgibosein pharmaceutical formulations.

The electrochemical detector (ECD) used for the substances that are either oxidizable or reducible and the electrical output results from an electron flow triggered by the chemical reaction that shows at the surface of the electrode. Recently, ECD analysed the content of glutathione in cancer cells. Fluorescence detector is most sensitive detectors among the LC detectors. One of the most important applications of fluorescence is the estimation of pharmaceuticals. Over a certain period of time most workers used the reversed- phase mode with UV absorbance detection whenever appropriate, because this provided the best available reliability, analysis time, repeatability and sensitivity. Several drugs have been assayed in pharmaceutical formulations and in biological fluids by using HPLC.

Thus, HPLC gives information many questions arise by the pharmaceutical industry. However, the limitations of HPLC include price of columns, solvents and a lack of long-term reproducibility due to the

proprietary nature of column packing. It became the method-of-choice for analytical support in many stages of quality control and assurance within the pharmaceutical industry. Recently HPLC-MS has been used for assay of drugs. In addition to its application in analysing the drugs HPLC alone and with hyphenated technique have been applied to analyse the impurities of the pharmaceuticals and degradation products.

3. INSTRUMENTAL ANALYSIS IN SOIL AND COMPOST MICROPLASTIC ASSESSMENT

We focused on studies that illustrated the benefits and drawbacks of both destructive (pyr/GC/MS, TED/GC/MS) and non-destructive (FTIR, SEM) methods of analysis in respect to the project's budget, timeline, and objectives. When choosing analytical procedures, researchers must consciously consider several factors, such as the goal or purpose of the project, the size of the study, the expected outcomes, turnaround time, and—above all—the type of analysis. These factors will determine which tool is most appropriate for the analysis. Similarly, the chemistry used in sample preparation prior to analysis affects sample characterization. Therefore, it can lead to a destructive method in which the sample is crushed, broken down or dissolved, or even combined with other materials before being characterized. In certain situations, characterization may be non-destructive because the sample is preserved. Each condition is unique to a specific piece of equipment when analyzing simple chemicals or complex polymers like MPs.

Figure 2.1. Microplastics analytical techniques and methods

3.1 MICROPLASTICS [MPS] IN AGRICULTURAL MATRICES

Agricultural matrices may involve multiple ecosystem components, making them potentially complicated. But soil and soil additives like compost are the foundation of agricultural systems, particularly farming. The issue of microplastics in soil as an environmental contaminant has received more attention lately. Given that studies have demonstrated that plastics have poor breakdown properties, larger plastic particles that stay in the soil decompose into smaller ones. Some studies have found MPs in soils. MPs can enter the soil in a variety of ways, including through the application of compost and sewage sludge. The application of soil improvements and direct contact with other anthropogenic activities make terrestrial habitats, particularly agricultural soils, more susceptible to high MP pollution. Although there is more published study on soil MPs than microplastic studies on compost, which is a potential source and conduit for plastic pollution entering the soil, information insufficiency persists despite substantial research on soil MPs. There are currently no standard operating procedures or protocols for the collection and analysis of samples for the evaluation of MP in soil and compost. One of the main reasons for the lack of knowledge in this area of study is the lack of standards.

3.2 VISUAL INSPECTION

visual analysis is a basic method of physical characterization in microplastic assessment. following the steps involved in MPs analysis in soil and compost, the identification of mps visually offers quite a simple approach to both scientists and non-experts. the naked eye identification, magnifying hand lens, and stereomicroscopes with an attachment of professional imaging software, as well as magnifying hand lens, are commonly used in optical identification and separation of MPs (1 mm–5 mm) from soil and composts. heat can also be applied to microscopy however, the experiment has limitations, as this effective thermal application was only verifiable on polyethylene (pe) and polypropylene (pp) from soil. there are several merits of the visual method of assessment, and it includes ease of carrying it out with little or no professionalism, cheap, and safe. nevertheless, smaller particle sizes (<1 mm) have proven to be more difficult to separate visually due to low confidence in colour or shape identification.

3.3 THERMAL TECHNIQUES

Another alternative to overcoming the issue of OM interference in spectroscopic analysis in MP assessment in soil and compost matrices is through thermal analytic technology, such as Pyr/GC/MS, and thermal extraction desorption gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (TED/GC/MS). Mass-based techniques are faster than FTIR and Raman, which could take days to analyze samples depending on the particle number, however, there is a loss of specific data on the particle size especially with the thermo-analytical technologies. Another advantage is that the concentrations of the MP particles can be measured in milligrams or grams of the sample. This properly measured specification enables easy comparison of results with other analyses and can be useful in the standardization of techniques, methods, and results. Since MPs can act as vectors by allowing the adsorption of chemical contaminants from the environment, thermal analytic technologies offer a direct, simple, and accurate MP contamination concentration analysis. Analysis of adsorbed chemicals onto MPs can be stressful and challenging, but necessary for environmental sustainability and human health.

However, this is a destructive analytical method, as the sample collected from the interested environmental matrix is completely pyrolyzed before being passed into the gas chromatography instrument for analysis. In the process of changing the state of the sample, some information is lost. Though not affected by OM presence, MP characterization such as shape, colour, and size cannot be known using this analytical method. Hence, if identifying such data is an objective in the research, then Pyr/GC/MS is not recommended. Another disadvantage is that this process cannot synchronously analyse different plastic particles, but only one MP type. Though no extraction process is involved, and this saves time, it is difficult to explain what happened to the impurities contained in the sample before pyrolysis took place. These impurities can create noise in the spectral readings and be mistaken for an actual reading of concerned chemicals. Pyr/GC/MS instrument is not commonly applied in soil MPs analysis as the physical counting of plastic particles is an important step in MPs analysis. Pre-treating the sample of OM interference, though possible, will be tedious and negate the simplicity, time saving, and ease of chromatography spectroscopic analysis. Also, there can be a risk of plastic fragmentation/degradation, as well as contamination if this is carried out Another thermal technology in MP analysis is thermal extraction desorption gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (TED/GC/MS), which has been shown to be efficient in detecting impurities and polymer types.

The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) technique analyses the mass loss of a plastic particle based on its degradation as a function of time or temperature. It is correlated with temperature because various plastic types have their distinct thermal degradation profile, and this degradation is directly related to the constant mass loss as a function of time. Some of the advantages of the TGA technique include its relatively low cost, no requirement of sample pretreatment, and simplicity to carry out. Nevertheless, this technique will not

allow for the continuation of studies on the same sample as it is destructive. A methodology based on both TGA analysis and statistical analysis called the Universal Soil Model (SUMM) was established by David et al. for the qualitative and quantitative identification of the most frequent MPs, such as PE, PS, PVC, and PET, in agricultural soil samples. Compared to the Py-GC-MS approach, the TGA analysis has a significant benefit since it uses a relatively high number of samples, which enables representative findings. MP studies have progressed based on combinative instrumentation analysis. This can be seen in Table 1, where some researchers combined two or more instruments for assessing the quantitative and qualitative data of MPs.

4. MICROPLASTICS LEGISLATION

The more preventive approach to the management of microplastic pollution in the environment is to enact laws and regulations that will help mitigate against the abundance of MPs in both the terrestrial and aquatic environments. Legislation is an important instrument to address MP pollution at all levels, including local, regional, national, and international. This is because as emerging pollutants, there are several uncertainties about MPs, especially the sources, distribution, fate, bioavailability, and toxicity to plants, animals, and humans; however, for the same knowledge paucity, it is difficult to develop suitable legislation. Legislation cannot be independent of knowledge and can also strengthen awareness. Over the/ past three decades, legislation has been developed to properly reduce the risks, impacts, and management of plastics, according to the three categories of larger plastics, medium plastics, and smaller plastics. However, for smaller plastics, where MPs belong, the focus has been more on preventing microbeads in aquatic environments.

MPs are categorized into two types, the primary MPs, and the secondary MPs. Primary MPs are more prevalent in aquatic environments as they are plastic particles that are deliberately created. They are usually found in wash-off household and industrial cleaning products, toothpaste, and cosmetics. Secondary MPs are plastic particles from the fragmentation of larger plastics over a long period of time. This MP type is abundant in the terrestrial environment as leftovers from microplastic waste. It is reported that the United Nations Environmental Program (UNEP) stated that the number of microbeads in an exfoliating gel could almost be the same number of plastics used in packaging the product. With microbeads abundant in the water, aquatic animals can ingest these plastics, which can threaten their lives, and potentially human health when taken up through the food chain, as MPs have been found to have the capability to translocate into the circulatory system and accumulate in human lungs, liver, and brain. This information on microbeads prompted some countries to enact laws to prohibit microbeads in cosmetic and cleaning products. The United States federal government established the Microbead-free Water Act of 2015 which became active in 2018, while the Canadian parliament passed legislation that prohibited the manufacture of microbeads in 2017, which brought a ban in 2019. In addition, the Australian Working Group, and the Council of the European Union joined in the fight against microbeads in the aquatic environments through legislation.

While there are legislations addressing microbeads in water bodies, this is insufficient as there are other forms of MPs in the environment. The legislation on larger plastics is a step in controlling and managing plastic wastes; however, there is a need for more since MPs can act as vectors, adsorbing microorganisms, heavy metals, and persistent organic pollutants. A study showed that globally, an average of 5 g of plastics is being ingested by people on a weekly basis. As shown in Table 4, some countries have placed bans and restrictions on the importation and production of plastic and fabric products. This action could help with reducing the number of secondary MPs in the terrestrial environment, including agricultural soil. MPs access the agricultural environment through the application of soil enhancers (biosolids, compost), mulch films, fragmentation of plastic packaging, irrigation, seed coating, and agrochemical encapsulates.

There is a need for more scientific research on MPs in the soil (terrestrial) environment as the progress reports will continually form the basis for improvement of regulations in restricting the increase in plastic

pollution. In addition, the fight against plastic pollution will be easier with the collaboration of every nation, organizations (including the plastic industry), and individuals. A month after the enforcement date of the Single-use Plastics Prohibition regulations, a group in Ontario, Canada successfully overturned the ban for single-use plastics (checkout bags, straws, cutlery, food packaging, and stir sticks). The court ruled against the ban, stating the prohibition of the plastics was “unreasonable” and “unconstitutional”. Also, while European states are jointly working to eradicate deliberate plastic waste in the environment, the United States only has about a third of the countries that are actively fighting against plastic pollution. It is still early to evaluate the effect of the legislations and regulations as they are only recently established, and have yet to be enforced in Canada; yet it is important to unite to achieve the desired goal of reduced plastics in the environment.

CONCLUSION

The main function of pharmaceutical medications is to prevent or cure potential illnesses in humans. The medication must be free of contaminants or any interference that could endanger people in order to fulfil its intended purpose. This review focuses on the function of different analytical tools in pharmaceutical assays and provides a comprehensive literature overview of the equipment used in pharmaceutical analysis. The paper also emphasizes how advanced approaches have evolved from the more traditional titrimetric method to the more sophisticated hyphenated techniques.

The many analytical methods for performing MP analysis are compiled and assessed in this paper. Because MP comes in so many different kinds, shapes, and forms, scientists still struggle with standardizing MP analysis methods. It is advised that scientists consider the research objectives and project budget when selecting the best instrumentation techniques for MPs analysis, even as they continue to investigate the possibility of creating a standardized instrumental process. MPs' global legislation needs to be given more consideration in order to reduce plastic pollution. As of 2018, more than 65% of nations worldwide had implemented regulations to combat the pollution caused by plastic bags.

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